

OPTIMAL FIBER PLACEMENT INCLUDING EFFECTS OF EMBROIDERY

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1 Introduction

Fiber orientation affects mechanical properties of composite laminates significantly as shown in Fig. 1, which illustrates that the strength of a carbon fiber reinforced plastic plate depends on the angle between the fiber and load direction. If the direction of the loads is different from the fiber by 5°, the strength reduces by more than 60% in this example. Accordingly, if the fibers can be placed along a desired path, the composite laminate plate can be designed more lightly and more optimally for some purposes. To this end tailored fiber placement (TFP) methods have been suggested [1-8]. Some researchers [1,2] use prepreg tows for processing the laminates, while others [3-8] use dry tows, in which the dry tows are placed on a substrate by using an embroidery machine and impregnated with resin. The former method uses costly prepregs, freezers to store them, and autoclaves to harden them, while the latter method does not use such materials and facilities and accordingly the composites processed by the latter method are expected to be lower-cost.

Oka et al. [7] proposed a design method for the embroidery-based TFP and verified its availability for a bending-torsion problem. It was also found that the effects of embroidery, such as eyes of a needle and thickness variation due to the fiber bundle orientation, played important roles on prediction of the mechanical properties of the composite laminates. In this paper a design method including such effects is proposed to predict the mechanical properties more precisely. To verify its availability, it is examined if eigenfrequencies of a composite plate can be controlled by designing the fiber bundle

orientation, and the error between calculation and experiment is evaluated.

2 Embroidery-based TFP

In this study the embroidery-based TFP method was applied. The embroidery machine used here is shown in Fig. 2 (Tajima, TCWM-101). When a desired path of the carbon fiber bundle is input to the embroidery machine, the machine places a continuous reinforcement fiber along the desired path on a substrate and processes a dry preform. A pair of the preforms was symmetrically put together as shown in Fig. 3, and impregnated with resin by using the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding method (VaRTM). Here a carbon fiber bundle (Toho Tenax, HTS40-12K) was used as the reinforcement fiber, plain woven carbon fabrics (Toho Tenax, W3101) with a stacking sequence of (45°/0°) were used as the substrate, and epoxy resin (Nagase Chemtex, XNR/H6815) was used as the resin.

3 Estimation of Elastic Moduli of Each Layer

Stiffness of the TFP layer is affected by the embroidery effects of not only the eyes of a needle and the thickness variation but also interval between neighboring fiber bundle paths and included threads. The interval, d , and the thickness, t , are related to the fiber bundle direction, θ , in the embroidery-based TFP.

$$d = d_0 \cos \theta, \quad (1)$$

where d_0 is the interval between the neighboring fiber bundle paths along the reference direction defined as $\theta = 0^\circ$ here, as shown in Fig. 4.

To predict the mechanical properties and to design the composite laminates having TFP layers more precisely, the effects of embroidery must be involved in the stiffness matrix of each layer. The stiffness matrix and the thickness must be given by functions of the fiber angle, θ , or the interval, d , and accordingly they must vary during the optimization design process.

The stacking sequence of the TFP laminate plates considered here was [TFPL/45°/0°]_s. TFPL represents the TFP layer and a pair of square brackets represents the laminates stitched together by the threads. Accordingly, the TFP laminate plates were comprised of pairs of TFP layers with the threads in the transversal direction and in-plane direction, plain woven layers in 45° direction with the threads in the transverse direction, and plain woven layers in 0° direction with the threads in the transverse direction and in-plane direction. These three layers are referred to as TFPL, PW_{mid}, and PW_{in}, respectively, as shown in Fig. 3.

To obtain the mechanical properties including the threads in each layer, [TFPL0°/45°/0°(d)]_s, [0°/0°(d)], [0°/0°(d)]_s, [0°/45°/0°(d)]_s were processed and the mechanical properties of the laminate plates were measured by tensile tests. TFPL0° represents the TFP layer with fiber bundles placed in the 0° direction on the substrate, and (d) represents the intervals of d mm. Although the interval between the bundle paths, d , is related to the fiber angle, θ , with Eq. (1) in the practical TFP laminate plates, only the interval was varied keeping the fiber angle in 0°, since the material properties of just the single TFP layers were needed to be evaluated here. The mechanical properties of each layer against the interval were calculated by using the classical laminate theory. In this study, the relationship between resultant forces and in-plane strains becomes

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N (Q_{ij})_k t_k,$$

$$(Q_{11})_k = \frac{E_{x,k}}{1 - \nu_{xy,k} \nu_{yx,k}},$$

$$(Q_{12})_k = \frac{\nu_{yx,k} E_{x,k}}{1 - \nu_{xy,k} \nu_{yx,k}},$$

$$(Q_{22})_k = \frac{E_{y,k}}{1 - \nu_{xy,k} \nu_{yx,k}},$$

$$(Q_{66})_k = \frac{1}{\frac{4}{E_{45,k}} - \frac{1}{E_{x,k}} - \frac{1}{E_{y,k}} + \frac{2\nu_{xy,k}}{E_{x,k}}}.$$

E and ν denote Young's modulus and Poisson ratio, respectively, and the subscripts k , x , y , and 45 represent the material constants in k -th layer, and those in the x , y , and 45° direction, respectively. N , ε , and γ denote the resultant force, in-plane normal strain, and in-plane shearing strain.

The specimens [TFPL0°/45°/0°(d)]_s, [0°/0°(d)], [0°/0°(d)]_s, [0°/45°/0°(d)]_s are referred to as TFP, PW2, PW4, and PW6, respectively. Here it was assumed that the thickness and the material constants for the corresponding layer were consistent in PW2, PW4, PW6, and TFP. More specifically, it was assumed that PW2 consisted of (PW_{sur})_s, PW4 consisted of (PW_{sur}/PW_{in})_s, PW6 consisted of (PW_{sur}/PW_{mid}/PW_{in})_s, and TFP consisted of (TFPL0°/PW_{mid}/PW_{in})_s. PW_{sur} represents the plain woven layer in 0° direction with the threads in the transverse direction and in-plane direction on the surface, and it was distinguished from PW_{in} because it had irregular surface due to the peel ply and the distribution medium for VaRTM. The mechanical properties of PW_{sur} can be obtained from PW2, PW_{in} from PW4 and the obtained properties of PW_{sur}, PW_{mid} from PW6 and the obtained properties of PW_{sur} and PW_{in}, and TFPL0° from TFP and the obtained properties of PW_{in} and PW_{mid}.

The tensile tests were carried out with a universal testing machine (Shimadzu, AG-5000B) following JIS K7164. The specimen size was 250mm×25mm. The 50mm regions of the both ends were clamped through sandpapers (#180) used as friction tabs. The

displacement rate was 1.0 mm/min. The strain was measured by strain gauges. The test was performed at room temperature 23°C. The tensile moduli were calculated within the range between 500με and 2500με. The intervals, d , of the specimens were set to 2.0 mm, 1.7 mm, 1.4 mm, 1.2 mm, and 1.0 mm, which corresponded to $\theta = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 53^\circ, \text{ and } 60^\circ$, respectively, because d_0 was set to 2.0 mm later. Four specimens for each in the $0^\circ, 45^\circ, \text{ and } 90^\circ$ direction were cut out from TFP plates, while four specimens for each in the 0° and 45° direction from PW2, PW4, and PW6 plates, because the properties in the 90° direction was assumed to be the same as those in the 0° direction.

Fig. 5 shows the elastic moduli for each laminate plate. Closed symbols, error bars, and lines represent mean, standard deviation, and approximation line, respectively. The properties for PW2, PW4, and PW6 can be assumed to be independent of the intervals, that is, amount of threads. The properties for TFP can be approximated by liner functions of the interval. The elastic modulus of TFP in the 0° direction increases as a decrease in the interval, while the elastic moduli in the 45° and 90° direction increase with an increase in the interval. The latter is attributed to the fact that the volume fraction of the TFP layer decreases and the volume fraction of the fibers in the 45° and 90° direction increases as the interval increases.

Substituting the obtained approximation values into the classical lamination theory, Eq. (2), the material constants in the longitudinal and transversal direction of the fiber were estimated. They are listed in Table 1. The subscript L and T represent the longitudinal and transverse direction of the fiber, G and ρ denote the shearing modulus and the density, respectively. The material constants of TFPL were assumed to be a linear function again.

Open symbols in Fig. 5(d) represent the elastic moduli recalculated with the estimated material constants for each layer listed in Table 1. The recalculated moduli are seen to be in good agreement with the measured values and that indicates the validity of the assumption.

4 Example Problem

To verify the availability of the proposed design method using the material constants including the embroidery effects obtained with the classical laminate theory, this method was applied to an example problem. In the example problem, eigenfrequencies of a [TFP/45°/0°]_s cantilever plate with a size of 150 mm by 100 mm as shown in Fig. 6 were controlled so that the first eigenfrequency became larger than 80 Hz and the difference between the first and the second eigenfrequency became as large as possible. This problem is specifically formulated as

$$\text{Find: } \boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{15}]$$

which minimalizes:

$$f(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = C - (Freq2 - Freq1);$$

$$(Freq2 - Freq1) / C \ll 1$$

subject to constrains: (3)

$$-60^\circ \leq \theta_i \leq 60^\circ \quad (i = 1, \dots, 15),$$

$$|\theta_j - \theta_{j-1}| \leq 15^\circ \quad (j = 2, \dots, 15),$$

$$Freq1 \geq 80\text{Hz}.$$

The cantilever plate was divided by 15 elements along the longitudinal direction. θ_i , $Freq1$, and $Freq2$ denote the fiber angle in the i -th element, the first, and the second eigenfrequency of the plate, respectively. The fiber angle θ_i was limited within $\pm 60^\circ$ and the difference in fiber angle between the neighboring elements within $\pm 15^\circ$.

For the optimization, the subproblem approximation method built in ANSYS ver. 12 was used. There, (1) $N+2$ sets of design variables were generated. N is the number of the design variables and equals 15 here. (2) The relationship between the objective function and the design variables and the relationship between the state variables and the design variables were estimated by curve fitting. (3) The set of design variables was found, which minimized the approximation curve of the objective function subject to the constrains by applying a sequential unconstrained minimization technique. Finally, (4) convergence was checked. This process was repeated with the new set of design variables until the solution was converged. If the solution was not converged after 500 cycles, the best solution was assumed to be an optimal solution here.

The solution around a local minimum of the object function was sometimes obtained. To find the global minimum, a kind of sweeping method was applied here. In the method, 2N design variable sets were generated manually, where a design variable was replaced with the minimum or the maximum value within the range of constraints with respect to the fiber angle and the rest of design variables were fixed to the values for the local optimal solution. The set of design variables which gave the best solution among the 2N design variable sets was used as an initial set and the optimization cycles of the subproblem approximation method were performed again. The best solution of the third optimization cycles was assumed to be the optimal solution of this problem.

The optimal path for this example problem is shown in Fig. 7 and the first and the second eigenfrequency in this case are listed in column "VAR" × line "OPT" in Table 2. The eigenfrequencies of the plates having TFP layers with a uniform fiber bundle angle of 0°, 45°, and 60° were also calculated. Of course, the eigenfrequencies were not controlled in these cases. The calculations were carried out by using the three kinds of material constant sets. One had material constants variable as functions of the interval between the fiber bundle paths, and the results are listed in the column "VAR". The others had material constants independent of the interval, where the material constants for the interval of 1 mm and 2mm were used and the results are listed in columns "1mm" and "2mm", respectively.

The first vibration mode was bending and the second vibration mode was twisting. It is seen from Fig. 7 that the fiber angle became close to 0° around the root and 50° around the middle of the plate. The former may affect increasing the first eigenfrequency and the latter may affect increasing the second eigenfrequency.

Looking at the column "VAR", it is seen that the constraint of the first eigenfrequency equal or more than 80 Hz is not satisfied for the plates with uniform fiber directions of "45°" and "60°", and that the plate with "OPT" placement of fibers is surely optimized for the objective function under the

constraints. The constraint of the first eigenfrequency is not satisfied for the plate even with "OPT" placement when the material constants set for "2mm" interval was used. This is because the fiber path of "OPT" was optimized using the material constants for "VAR" and E_L and t for "2mm" is equal or less than "VAR". The calculated eigenfrequencies of "1mm" or "2mm" are different from "VAR". In this table, the maximum error is approximately 50% between the material constants of "VAR" and "1mm" at the first eigenfrequency for the plate with fibers placed in uniform direction of 0°.

The validity of the predicted results was verified by comparing to experimental results. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 8. A specimen was clamped by a vice. Vibration was generated by giving an impact with a hammer. The vibration was measured by a strain gauge, a bridge box (Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo SB-121A), and a dynamic strain meter (Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo, DA-37A) and recorded in a digital oscilloscope (Yokogawa, DL-708E). The eigenfrequencies were calculated in the digital oscilloscope. The obtained eigenfrequencies are also listed in the column "EXP" in Table 2.

The measured eigenfrequencies in "EXP" agree well with "VAR", which have a margin of error of approximately 10% due to manufacturing errors of the plates for the example problem and the plates for measurement of the material constants, the assumption for estimation of the material constants, and so on. Moreover, "OPT" is approximately optimal in the experiment, although the constraint of the first eigenfrequency is not satisfied because of the errors. The first eigenfrequency cannot be known before the experiment. Such a value might not be adequate to be included in the constraints because experiments involve errors. Nevertheless, when a structural optimization must be carried out with such constraints, the error margin should be considered.

5 Conclusion

A design method for TFP layers processed by an embroidery machine was improved by considering the effects of embroidery such as the eyes of a needle, the threads, the thickness variation, and the interval variation between the neighboring fiber

bundle paths. To estimate the material constants of each layer the classical laminate theory was applied. It was seen that the material constants of TFP layer could be assumed to be a linear function of the interval and those of the plain woven layers could be assumed to be constant. Using the estimated material constants, a structural optimization analysis was carried out. By considering the effects of embroidery, the result was improved. The prediction agreed well with the experiment, differing by approximately 10% due to the manufacturing error and the assumption. Therefore, when a structural optimization is carried out, the error margin should be taken into account.

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Table 1 Estimated material constants for each layer.

	PW _{in}	PW _{mid}	TFPL(<i>d</i> [mm])
E_L [GPa]	54.5	59.7	$-14.2d+154.5$
E_T [GPa]	-	-	$1.9d+4.7$
ν_{LT}	0.08	0.12	$0.02d+0.34$
ν_{TL}	-	-	$0.008d+0.009$
G_{LT} [GPa]	3.6	5.2	$0.4d+3.8$
t [mm]	0.26	0.23	$-0.3d+1.1$
ρ [g/cm ³]	1.4	1.3	$-0.09d+1.69$

Table 2 First and second eigenfrequencies in Hz for various laminate plates and for various sets of material constants and experiment.

Orientation		1mm	2mm	VAR	EXP
0°	1st	164	110	110	101
	2nd	256	204	204	184
45°	1st	62	51	58	52
	2nd	267	227	252	224
60°	1st	49	42	49	54
	2nd	226	198	226	236
OPT	1st	95	73	80	72
	2nd	297	242	260	230

Fig. 1. Variation of strength against the angle between the fiber and load direction.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the laminate with stacking sequence $[TFPL/45^0/0^0]_s$. Red lines represent the stitched threads.

Fig. 2. Embroidery machine. Tajima TCWM-101.

Fig. 4. Variation of interval between the neighboring fiber bundle paths due to the fiber bundle angle.

Fig. 5. Elastic moduli of the various laminate plates. Closed symbols, error bars, and lines represent mean, standard deviation, and approximation line, respectively. Open symbols in (d) represent the elastic moduli recalculated by using the estimated material constants for each layer listed in Table 1.

Fig. 6. Cantilever plate of the example problem.

Fig. 7. Optimal fiber bundle paths.

Fig. 8. Experimental setup for the measurement of eigenfrequencies.